

Issues with Credit Rating: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

The surge in Indian corporate debt default has been a debated issue of discussion among finance professionals. The discussion sparked off in 2019 when, SEBI, for the first time ever, slapped a fine of Rs.25 lakh each on three of India's leading credit rating agencies, specifically, India Ratings Research Private Limited, CARE, and ICRA (SEBI, 2019). Debt instruments with famous names like Amtek Auto, Essel, Reliance Com, Dewan Housing Finance, JP Morgan Debt Fund, and IF&LS have defaulted lately, shaking the security market's confidence deeply. The defaults occurred notwithstanding solid ratings from the main credit rating agencies. This paper reviews recent literature on credit rating issues in the backdrop of the disturbing events. The review states that credit rating has an important role to play in regulating the capital markets. However, the literature is by and large silent on the fraudulent practices by the agencies that have led to the loss of confidence of the investors.

KEYWORDS: Credit rating, Bonds, Literature review.

1. INTRODUCTION

Credit ratings address rating agencies' perspectives about credit risk, which is the limit and eagerness of a borrower or a debt security guarantor, such as a partnership, state, or regional government, to meet its monetary commitments. Moreover, credit rating agencies (CRAs) further distribute ratings concerning the credit nature of explicit issues, such as a bond or other debt commitment, and the relative probability that it may default. Of late, there has been a series of debt failures despite a sound credit rating by the leading agencies. In the backdrop of this paradox, the paper looks at some of the recent literature in this regard.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Liu (2020) stated that customer credit rating adopts scientific methods & standardized procedures to investigate, evaluate, analyze, measure & review rating objects' capacity. The objective of the system is to fulfil corresponding economic commitments. Currently, big data enhances the data source of credit data that outperforms that of traditional financial data. This paper begins with the concept of enterprise credit rating system, through the comprehension of credit rating system & the combination with big data, to comprehend the current issues & the reasons for China's current credit rating system.

Pan *et al.* (2020) stated that this paper predominantly portrays credit rating agencies' function & their effect on the capital market and credit rating agencies' role in the financial crisis. This paper makes a progression of investigations on the failure of credit rating agencies to utilize the early warning function of credit rating, && advances three issues of credit rating agencies, including improper handling of irreconcilable circumstances for rating business, poor rating quality, & absence

of transparency in the operation of credit rating agencies. The absence of transparency in the internal process & content of rating, the absence of comparable data between the rating of traditional goods & undifferentiated structured goods, & the absence of comparable data on the operation performance of credit rating agencies is the causes for the absence of transparency in the operation of credit rating agencies, as well as the significant reasons for the financial storm.

Chen *et al.* (2020) stated that a core issue of fast-developing online lending is to build up a sound credit rating method for borrowers. When examining 14,558 recovery rates of defaulted assets relating to every borrower of the Renrendai platform from 2011 to 2016, the researchers find that the current credit rating system (7 levels from A.A., A, B, C, D, E & H.R.) cannot distinguish the distribution of recovery rates. In like manner, this study proposes a credit rating approach for online lending platforms utilizing a Chinese sample. Online lending has definitely created more in China than in other countries & regions. Initially, by referring to the US FICO Credit systems & Sesame Credit, fifteen indices are selected. Secondly, the K-Means clustering credit rating method utilizing recovery rate is utilized to reclassify the borrowers, addressing the issue that Renrendai's credit rating system cannot distinguish borrowers with assets of different recovery rates. In any case, this simple reclassification leads to another problem that borrowers with high credit ratings are over borrowers with low credit ratings (the well-known "inverted pyramid" problem). Accordingly, an augmented credit rating method is finally created to reclassify borrowers, integrating K-Means clustering & factor analysis utilizing recovery rate. A clear distinction between borrowers with different recovery rates is quite easily possible by utilizing this finalized method.

Torrejon (2020) stated that the on-going debate over how strictly the financial markets & their participants ought to be regulated after the outbreak of the 2008 financial crisis had carried extraordinary regard for Credit Rating Agencies' case. Credit Rating Agencies are essential for the working of the worldwide financial markets. Trusting experts with the necessary tools & experience to lead assessments on the creditworthiness & risk of financial instruments is more compelling than letting investors make their credit risk assessment one by one. Consequently, financial institutions in the E.U. & the U.S had for a long time depended on these agencies to assess the credit risk of the financial markets, giving them both regulatory powers & a high degree of leverage, while the agencies themselves stayed unregulated. Notwithstanding, inflated ratings on debt instruments such as Mortgage-Backed Securities in the early 2000s that ended up being useless are among the reasons for the 2008 economic crisis. The monstrous minimizing of Mortgage-Backed Securities following the eruption of the housing market bubble in 2007 set off the frenzy, causing the dry-up of financial markets & the bankruptcy of numerous companies. Therefore, since the economic turmoil of 2008, controllers on both sides of the Atlantic concurred that stricter regulation & oversight of the Credit Rating Agencies were required to avoid a similar economic disaster in the future. Therefore, a series of new regulations have been passed in both the E.U. & the U.S. They are planned to improve the quality & integrity of the Credit Rating Agencies by tending to the issues presented by them & that contributed to the making of the crisis. Be that as it may, understanding how to fix the Credit Rating Agencies' issues while protecting the useful role they play as gatekeepers of the financial markets is proving to be a laborious & complex err&. In this study, the researcher will discuss the regulations towards Credit Rating Agencies presented after the crisis in the E.U. & the U.S, & dissect how much they are effectively addressing the Credit Rating industry's malfunctions.

Shi *et al.* (2019) stated that their paper proposes a credit rating model that factors the effect of some of the key macroeconomic variables on the commercial banks' credit decisions & also on loss given default (LGD). The results give additional insight into the phenomena that under certain conditions, a higher credit rating may still lead to higher LGD. The research was based on actual bank data from 2,044 farmers from China. The theoretical analysis & empirical verification gives key experiences into the regulatory & commercial banks' credit policy in a developing country setting while simultaneously assisting with easing micro & small credit entities' financing issues.

Ding *et al.* (2019) stated that to adjust to the genuine circumstance of the complex network environment & make the credit rating results increasingly unique & true. The researchers classified the transaction history of sellers' into various time frames & define four concepts, including recent credit, cumulative negative credit, long-term credit & evaluator credibility. The model is progressively appropriate for the credibility & reliability of the credit compared to the traditional credit rating model. Through examining the current credit rating platform, this paper analyzes the current issues & the advantages of the system itself & sets up a new credit model by considering numerous kinds of factors, which incorporate various objective factors, such as the amount of time required for completion of the transaction, the purchaser's credit standing, & so on. In the end, the Implementation of the proposed credit rating model is recommended based on the above components.

Zhang *et al.* (2019) stated that in this paper, the researchers investigate the issue of credit rating management in energy trading amongst micro grids subject to transmission losses & wheeling cost. The principal concern is how to constrain retailers' default behaviours to empower all the consumers & retailers to be effectively engaged in energy trading. By supplying retailers as leaders & consumers as followers, the researchers establish a multi-leader multi-follower dynamic game model & propose a scorecard model dependent on logistic regression to assess retailers' credit ratings. The concept of trust degree is then applied to all the retailers as a punishment measure to link their credit ratings to reduce profit. With such a strategy, the researchers can theoretically show that some unique equilibrium exists for the dynamic game model. The best response algorithm is recommended to make the retailers & consumers accomplish the equilibrium iteratively. Numerical simulations are given to demonstrate the efficiency & effectiveness of the proposed method. It is discovered that default behaviours of selfish retailers can be incredibly compelled with only a little degradation of other participant's interests, along these lines advancing the establishment of a trustworthy trading market. The researchers also discuss the impact level of losses due to transmission on retailers & consumers' trading behaviours.

Gusarova *et al.* (2019) stated that in modern theory & practice of banking, there are different ways to assessing credit rating, depending on the category of clients. Considering the absence of unity of methodology, credit institutions build up their methods for assessing credit rating, considering the Central Bank & the Basel Committee's suggestions. Most of the methods depend on a system of indicators that assesses the liquidity, turnover, profitability & financial stability of the borrower. Investigation of statistical data permits concluding about the growth of overdue debts of the populace & enterprises to commercial banks, which is proof of the imperfect methods utilized by credit institutions to evaluate credit rating. Based on a study of the positive & negative sides of different methods & ratings of expert opinions, the study creates recommendations for improving credit rating methods utilized in AB Devon-Credit in modern economic conditions. The study depends on positive & negative aspects of different methods & expert assessment.

Stellinga (2019) stated that the 2008 crisis clarified that credit rating agencies (CRAs) could contribute to systemic financial risk. Shockingly, post-crisis reforms have scarcely tended to the hidden issues, including rating agencies' methodologies, their ratings' homogeneity, & widespread market reliance on these signals. Current scholarship on CRA regulation accuses policymakers' unwillingness to fix systemic issues. This article draws on key findings from the social studies segment of finance literature to give an alternate explanation: the key obstacle is that the policymakers cannot fix these issues. The regulatory issue stems from performativity: the risk assessments (including the ratings) shape the risks, which they imply to depict. Adding to this literature, the article explains how performativity limits credit rating changes by making radical reforms possibly harmful. Standardizing the methodologies or setting up of a public CRA could perhaps strengthen ratings' homogeneity. Replacing ratings in regulation with market-based indicators may make more terrible systemic issues. The article then empirically details how the E.U. policymakers, faced with these dilemmas, ultimately avoided major changes.

Partnoy (2017) stated that scholars & regulators generally agree that credit rating agency failures were at the focal point of the recent financial crisis. Congress reacted to these failures through some reforms in the 2010 Dodd-Frank Act. This article shows that those reforms have fizzled. Rather, regulators have thwarted Congress's intent at every turn. Subsequently, the major credit rating agencies keep on being gigantically profitable yet generate little or no informational value. The key issues that prompted the financial crisis- over-reliance on credit ratings, an absence of oversight & accountability, & primitive methodologies- stay as significant as they existed before the financial crisis. This article tends to each of these issues & proposes several solutions. Although Congress endeavoured to evacuate "regulatory licenses" to the credit rating agency, the references to ratings in different statutes & rules, regulatory reliance on ratings stay unavoidable. This article shows that regulated institutions keep on depending mechanistically on ratings & exhibits that regulations continue to reference ratings, notwithstanding the Congressional mate to expel references. This article proposes a few ways to lessen reliance. Second, although Congress approved new oversight measures, including an Office of Credit Ratings (OCR), that oversight has been inadequate. Annual investigations have revealed various failures, many in the same mortgage-related areas that precipitated the financial crisis. However, regulators have imposed minimal discipline on violators. Moreover, because regulators refuse to recognize particular rating agencies in OCR reports, wrongdoers do not endure reputational costs. This article proposes changes to the OCR that would upgrade its independence & hone the effect of its investigations. Third, although Congress authorized new accountability measures, especially expelling rating agencies' exemptions from liability under

section eleven of the Securities Act of 1933 & Regulation F.D., the Securities & Exchange Commission has gutted both of those provisions. The SEC played out an end-run around Dodd-Frank's explicit requirements, switching the express will of Congress litigation has not been compelling as an accountability measure, either, in part because rating agencies keep on attesting the dubious argument that ratings are protected speech. This article contends that the SEC should reverse course & actualize Congress's intent, including empowering private litigation.

Anwar (2016) stated that Small & Medium Enterprises (SMEs) contribute to economic development worldwide. Research demonstrates that the main challenge for getting loans is data asymmetry between external creditors & SMEs themselves. This makes SMEs investment increasingly unsafe & vulnerable for the investors. In this circumstance, credit rating agencies play a significant role by rating the SMEs that replicates SMEs' overall creditworthiness. This paper aims to recognize major problems & prospects of SMEs financing & SMEs' comparative rating process in Bangladesh. Currently, credit rating agencies in Bangladesh follow the comparative procedure as in Japan & India. A major issue emerges because rating fees are the key revenue source for credit rating agencies, which implants an irreconcilable situation of marking high ratings. Moreover, Bangladesh still could not set up institutions in developed countries, e.g., such as Credit Guarantee Corporations (CGC), that bolster SMEs as a credit guarantor in Japan. Aside from this, the Bangladesh government may support boosting investor pay or subsidized model (this is a practice in India) that builds SMEs rating.

Colla et al. (2019) stated that they review the literature on debt structure, a central element in a firm's capital structure. The researchers first survey theoretical & empirical research relating to debt characteristics – maturity & priority – & debt types – bank loans, credit lines, corporate bonds, commercial paper, & capital leases. The researchers then present comprehensive empirical proof on public U.S. firms' debt structure over the period 2002-2018, featuring that over 3-quarters of U.S. firms concentrate their borrowing in one debt type, & offer some suggestive clarifications for the observed pattern. Finally, the researchers discuss directions for future research, including a superior comprehension of debt structure choices by non-U.S. firms & by private firms, the cross-sectional & temporal variations in debt structure, the corporate policy ramifications of firms' debt structure choices, & the connection between types of assets & debt structure.

Bae et al. (2018) examined the impact of corporate social responsibility (CSR) activities on loan spreads of syndicated bank loans, with a specific interest in how CSR & credit ratings are interconnected as a joint determinant of loan spreads. Concentrating on private debt contracts, the researchers show that both CSR strengths & concerns are related to their loan spreads. CSR strengths work to bring down firm risk, subsequently lessening the loan spread, whereas CSR concerns increase firm risk, in this way expanding the loan spread. Once the researchers incorporate detailed credit rating information in the models, CSR concerns lose significance, but CSR strengths remain significantly related to the spread in the loan. The researchers likewise found that CSR concerns & CSR strengths are related to the loan spread for the non-rated firms. However, the CSR concern impact is stronger than the CSR strength impact for these firms. A further test shows that firm risk estimated by stock return volatility plays a direct channel through which a firm's CSR activities influence loan spreads, whose outcome lends further support to our main results. Overall, the researcher's outcomes give strong evidence proving that CSR is an important factor in the pricing of loan contracts beyond the credit rating information & the outcomes stay vigorous to the possible firm size effect & the endogeneity issues.

Ghosh (2017) stated that credit rating agencies assess the creditworthiness of specific debt instruments. To decide a bond's rating, a credit rating agency investigates the issuer's accounts & the legal agreements connected to it to produce the chance of default, anticipated misfortune, or a similar metric. The metrics fluctuate between agencies. The downgrade & upgrade of ratings are known as notching. A matrix of transition probabilities signifies the probability of single & multiple notching. The matrix is defined to depict the probability for change in an underlying rating. Rating migration alludes to a change from an initial rating to a new rating category. The transition matrix signifies the possibility of a company moving from one credit rating to another, i.e., the chance of a firm's credit quality improving or intensifying. It signifies moving possibilities from one rating level to all other ratings, including default for a given rating & time horizon. It shows the total possible states that a rating can take over a given time horizon & consequently gives detailed information on rating movements. When the credit quality of corporate bonds exacerbates, the possibility of future default also increases. The researcher has estimated the transition matrix for companies rated by ICRA utilizing two estimation procedures based on historical transitions - The cohort approach & Risk approach - utilizing five years' data from Bloomberg between 2012 & 2017.

DeHaan. (2017) stated that credit ratings on numerous financial instruments failed to depict default risk before the global financial crisis precisely. The researcher finds no decrease in the performance of corporate credit ratings during or after the crisis, showing that the failures of ratings on financial instruments were because of conditions unique to the rating agencies' financial instruments divisions. Alternatively, maybe, the preponderance of tests shows that corporate credit rating performance improves after the crisis, steady with the rating agencies positively reacting to public criticism & regulatory pressures. Simultaneously, the researcher finds evidence of sophisticated market participants diminishing their reliance on corporate credit ratings after the crisis. Steady with theoretical models of reputation cyclicity; a likely explanation is that the rating agencies experience spill over reputation damage from their failed financial instruments ratings. The researcher examination informs regulators, practitioners, & academics about the exhibition of corporate credit ratings during & after the crisis & furnishes novel empirical evidence consistent with reputation concerns influencing credit rating usage decisions.

Ligeti *et al.* (2016) stated that credit rating agencies formulate publicly accessible opinions on debtors' capacity & willingness to repay debts. This way, they lessen the information asymmetry between creditors & borrowers. Due to regulatory endeavouring recent years, credit rating processes have become progressively more transparent as credit rating agencies publish their methodology & make accessible the values calculated for the most significant key variables. This study is expected to inspect the extent to which the indicative rating range resulting from the methodology at the current level of transparency clarifies the experimentally observed credit rating of sovereigns. The authors determined a rating range of 3 notches & found that in the case of S&P, a higher ratio of observed credit ratings fell within this range & permitted for the reconstruction of individual steps, while Moody's & Fitch's presently accessible methodologies proved to be less suited for such a reconstruction.

3. FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

Researchers have highlighted credit rating agencies' role in providing professional information to investors to make informed decisions. Post the 2008 financial crisis importance of credit rating agencies' role has gone up and are expected to support the regulatory efforts in the capital markets. They are expected to follow standard procedures and practices while rating a financial instrument. Professionalism should be adopted while following these practices. However, some of the recent events, including the defaults of the debt instruments in the Indian capital markets, point out that all is not well with the credit rating agencies. More research is certainly warranted in this area to find out the exact reasons for this failure. Researchers need to find out if the failure is systemic and also suggest mechanisms to plug the loopholes.

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